

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF "POETIC CINEMA" TRADITIONS IN UZBEK FEATURE FILMS

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Abstract. *The given article discusses how by the second half of the 1960s, a new generation emerged at "Uzbekfilm" studio, full of enthusiasm during the period known as the "thaw." Due to the creative endeavors of young filmmakers, the traditions of "poetic cinema" began to take shape. The article also highlights the unique characteristics of films produced between the 1960s and 1990s.*

Keywords: *poetic cinema, feature film, art house, director, screenwriter, actor, film studio, film manifesto, cinema, film comedy.*

Introduction

It is important to suggest that by the mid-1960s, a new generation full of enthusiasm from the "Thaw" period had emerged at the "Uzbekfilm" studio. They began engaging not only with the realities around them but also with dramatic models rooted in cultural and national traditions. During this period, the creative activity of directors such as Shuhrat Abbosov, Elyor Eshmukhamedov, Ravil Batirov, Damir Salimov, and Ali Hamroyev; screenwriters like Odilsho Agishev and Uchkun Nazarov; and cinematographers such as Dilshod Fathullin, Hotam Fayziyev, and Davron Salimov, was marked by an intensive search for artistic means and cinematic possibilities. Their goal was to portray the characters more deeply and authentically.

Methodology

It would not be accurate to consider the generation of the 1960s as a single, like-minded artistic community united under a common aesthetic program. Nevertheless, despite differences in age and artistic interests, these filmmakers consciously strived to elevate national cinema to a level that met international standards.

During this period, Uzbek cinema presented the world with several meaningful and vivid films. The film "Mahallada duv-duv gap" does not belong to art-house cinematic manifestos. It can rather be classified as a simple domestic comedy. It was the debut feature-length film of the young, relatively unknown Uzbek director Shuhrat Abbosov. Just as it is impossible to predict which film will become a masterpiece, artistic success especially in cinema cannot be pre-planned.

In this film, Abbosov clearly demonstrates a desire to blend theater and cinema. The content of "Mahallada duv-duv gap" stood out from many other films shown in theaters at the time. It realistically depicted the daily lives of residents in a mahalla (neighborhood), where traditional adobe houses stood side-by-side with newly built apartment blocks. The film faithfully portrayed the joys and concerns of these people. It was notable for its broad and unusual plot, and its artistic impact was significantly enhanced by Manas Leviev's superbly composed, vivid, and emotionally resonant music.

The film of Shuhrat Abbosov "Mahallada duv-duv gap" became a unique symbol of the "new wave" in Uzbek cinema. His later films, such as "You Are Not an Orphan" (1962) and "Sun in Your

Heart” (1965), carried poetic tones that opened the way for auteur cinema and became one of the main trends in the development of Uzbekistan’s cinematic art.

The emergence of the “auteur film” genre was closely tied to attempts to reflect the complex contradictions of modern society through a new cinematic language. This direction found expression in films by Ali Hamroyev such as “The Stork Has Come, Summer Has Arrived” (a domestic drama, 1966), “The Fan” (a lyrical novella, 1973), and “A Man Follows the Birds” (a cinematic legend, 1975). The director further developed these tendencies in historical-revolutionary genres through films like “*The Extraordinary Commissar*” (historical-revolutionary, 1970), “Courage” (drama, 1971), and “The Seventh Bullet” (revolutionary-adventure “eastern,” 1972).

Results and discussion

During this period, several comedy films were also produced. The audience's desire for entertainment and relaxation was fulfilled through films such as “*We Will Meet at the Stadium*” (directed by Z. Sobitov, 1956), “I’m in Love” (directed by Y. Azamov, 1958), “Mahallada duv-duv gap” (directed by Sh. Abbosov, 1960), “Sinchalak” (directed by L. Fayziyev, 1961), and “Yor-Yor” (directed by A. Hamroyev, 1964).

Overall, these films were cinematic anthologies featuring well-known actors from cinema, theater, and pop music. The film “*I’m in Love*” (*Maftuningman*), which was shot according to attractive and original comedy standards, enriched its calm and balanced storylines with themes of love and romance, as well as with music and songs. The film became a model of a unique genre on the national screen and later turned into an object of imitation. This is confirmed by the numerous remakes—some successful, others less so.

The film “*Yor-Yor*”, shot in 1964 at the “Uzbekfilm” studio, was directed by a very young Ali Hamroyev. In this comedy, which showcased some of the most beautiful landscapes of Uzbekistan, the main roles were played by S. Khojaev, R. Khamroev and B. Ikhtiyorov.

The theme of Tashkent became a central subject in the creative tandem of young filmmakers Elyor Eshmukhamedov and Odilsho Agishev. In their 1967 film “*Delicacy*” (*Nafosat*), the city of Tashkent, the Anhor Canal, and the motif of parting with childhood were presented with great success elements that would later reappear throughout their subsequent films. In “*Nafosat*”, the urban landscape found its cinematographic identity for the first time. Through conversations that conveyed character, situation, and a sense of time, the film portrayed the subtle materialities of everyday life.

The events of the film were brought together in a chain of emotional stories forming a lyrical narrative about love, friendship, and the complex issues of the surrounding world. The director did not limit himself only to depicting the characters’ lives and psychological states.

In the fates of the main characters of this film Sanjar, Temur, Lena and Mamura their life paths always intersect unexpectedly and seemingly by chance, as if deliberately arranged. This element, presented in a fresh and original interpretation, captivates the audience.

Elyor Eshmukhamedov and Odilsho Agishev’s second work, “*Lovers*” (*Sevishganlar*, 1969), develops the themes raised in their previous film—unrestrained love, emotional subtlety, sincerity, and a willingness to sacrifice oneself. In the film’s simple visual structure, the camera lens plays the role of an observer. Together with their “observer,” the authors express their love for the city of Tashkent—a place where representatives of different nationalities, who together form humanity, meet and where everything seems possible.

The central idea of the film is overcoming the boundaries and barriers that separate people from one another. The main roles were played by young actors who have since become stars Rustam Sagdullaev, Rodion Nakhapetov, Anastasia Vertinskaya, and Shuhrat Ergashev. It is also worth

speaking more about the supporting actors, because spotting the brief appearances of actors like Hamza Umarov, Bakhtiyor Ikhtiyorov, Melis Abzalov, Javlon Hamroev, Vladimir Baramikov, and Nellya Ataullaeva among the crowd is especially enjoyable.

After the great success of lyrical films about young Tashkent residents at both the all-Union and international levels, film director Elyor Eshmukhamedov, in collaboration with screenwriters Odilsho Agishev and Javlon Iskhaqov, returned to their familiar characters in the films “Oh, What a Time We Had!” (1981), “Farewell, My Foolish Youth!” (1985), and “With Love and Pain” (1988). These films reflect scenes of everyday life communal apartments, old Tashkent courtyards, and summer cinemas and offer a vivid, socially meaningful portrayal of the inner atmosphere of those difficult years, giving them significant cultural value.

The national, cultural, and religious diversity of the characters in these urban ballads, as well as the contrasts in their aspirations and interests, are also noteworthy. Later works by Shuhrat Abbosov, Ali Hamroyev, and Elyor Eshmukhamedov began to exhibit unique features that marked important stages in the development of the “Uzbek poetic wave.”

Ali Hamroyev’s work became a significant phenomenon in the cinematography of this period. His films are characterized by polystylism and a dominance of various genre and visual solutions. While his film “The Stork Has Come, Summer Has Arrived” (1966) was made in a poetic style, “A Man Follows the Birds” (1975) stood out for its lyrical and subjective tonality. Among his most striking and concise films is “The Fan” (1973), followed by the existentialist drama “Triptych” (1979).

The detailed themes of Ali Hamroyev’s films are primarily executed within the genre of social melodrama. In Ali Hamroyev’s work, one of the greatest achievements of national cinematography was realized—the skillful integration of mass appeal and social critique, which came to be seen as a guarantee of audience engagement. It must be noted that, in response to Hollywood’s Western genre, the director actively developed a new cinematic genre through his historical-revolutionary films such as “The Extraordinary Commissar” (1970) and “The Seventh Bullet” (1972).

During the 1970s, a number of films were produced that focused on individuals establishing their personal lives, including “Summer Rain” (directed by A. Kabulov, 1970), “We Are Waiting for You, Young Man” (1972), “A House Under the Scorching Sun” (directed by G. Bzarov and Z. Roizman, 1977), and “Duel Under the Plane Tree” (directed by M. Abzalov, 1978). Toward the end of this decade, a more somber tone and attention to the “forbidden” aspects of reality began to emerge in films.

In “*The Remarkable Dreamer*” (directed by R. Batirov, 1977) and “*Triptych*” (directed by A. Hamroyev, 1979), the absurdity of Soviet life and the fates of those who thought differently within “the system” were portrayed with striking realism. Films such as “My Dear Person” (directed by R. Batirov, 1973), “Reunions and Separations” (directed by E. Eshmukhamedov, 1973), “A Man Follows the Birds” (directed by A. Hamroyev, 1975), “The Bitter Seed” and “The Savage” (directed by K. Kamolova, 1975 and 1988), and “Hail” (directed by U. Nazarov, 1979) presented the destinies of gifted individuals and the moral cost of conscience in a delicate, existential form.

By the second half of the 1980s, there was a renewed and growing interest in the on-screen portrayal of the image of the young contemporary an interest that extended to deep analysis and nuanced cinematic expression. The sociopolitical environment that emerged during this period demanded that cinema reflect more sensitively the changes occurring in society. The rigid frameworks that had been long accepted began to gradually erode. Characters were no longer portrayed as strictly “positive” or “negative”; instead, films began to present protagonists who

embodied the real contradictions of life, social inequalities, and the full spectrum of human traits both good and bad.

As creators became increasingly concerned with the pressing issues of their time and sought to draw public attention to unfolding events, the burden of responsibility placed on the protagonist grew heavier. Although not the sole element determining a film's impact, the figure of a socially active hero became one of the key features influencing its resonance with the broader public.

While the 1960s–70s in Uzbek cinema were characterized by poetic, lyrical-subjective tendencies and a generally optimistic interpretation of reality, by the late 1980s, filmmakers began to address the sociopolitical transformations in society and the growing negative phenomena within its moral and social fabric. Films emerged that told stories about these darker aspects, including “*Paralysis*” (dir. E. Eshmukhamedov, 1988), “*Pilaf*” (dir. S. Boboyev, 1987), “*Wolves*” (dir. S. Nazarmukhamedov, 1987), “*The Creature or the Other*” (dir. A. Fathullin, 1988), “*Barkhan*” (dir. S. Boboyev, 1989), “*Meeting in Samara*” (dir. Sh. Abbosov, 1989), and “*Who Are You?*” (dir. J. Fayziyev, 1989). These narrative films, which often took on a dystopian quality, placed the author's personal, subjective perspective on surrounding reality and societal issues at the forefront. They emphasized the vast chasm between the widely accepted idealized vision of a “bright Soviet future” and the helplessness experienced in real life.

By the late 1980s during the period of *Perestroika* a new generation of film directors entered the cinematic scene, including D. Fayziyev, S. Boboyev, Yu. Roziqov, R. Malikov, N. Abbosov, Z. Musoqov, J. Qosimov, and B. Odilov. These filmmakers actively pursued new philosophical and stylistic approaches. The collapse of traditions associated with the Soviet model was reflected not only in themes and ideas but also in plot structures and narrative frameworks.

Conclusion

In conclusion, directors of this period began to create films on topics that had previously been censored or prohibited. Furthermore, in terms of form and style, they rejected the aesthetic practices of the older generation. Genre and stylistic shifts, inevitable in Uzbek cinema, were still ahead—but the groundwork for those changes was now being laid.

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